

Sample 32a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0047
	{Si}	64.0
	{Al, Si}	7.2
	{Fe}	5.4
	{Ti}	4.7
	{S, Ba-LA1}	3.3
	{Si, Fe}	2.0
	{Ca}	1.7
	{Mg, Si}	1.5
	{Al}	1.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.8
	{Al, Si, K}	0.8
	{Si, S, Ba-LA1}	0.7
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.7
	{Si, Fe}	0.7
	{S, Ba-LA1, Ba-LB1}	0.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.6
	{S}	0.5
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, P}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{P}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.1
Pellet	0.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.1
Olivine flux	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.6
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	8.4
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
Carbon rich - other	1.3
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	61.4
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	22.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	1.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.7
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.3
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.6
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	8.4
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.3
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	61.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	22.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	1.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.2

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 32b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0028
	{Si}	66.9
	{Al, Si}	7.6
	{Fe}	4.8
	{Ti}	4.0
	{S, Ba-LA1}	2.7
	{Ca}	2.2
	{Si, Fe}	1.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.4
	{Al, Si, K}	1.0
	{Mg, Si}	0.8
	{Al}	0.7
	{Si, S, Ba-LA1}	0.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.6
	{Mg, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.5
	{Si, Fe}	0.5
	{S}	0.5
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{S, Ba-LA1, Ba-LB1}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{P, Ca}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Mg, Al}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.0
	{P}	0.0
	{Na, Al}	0.0
	{Zn-LA1}	0.0
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	15.7
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.3
Carbon rich - other	2.2
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	52.6
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	25.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	1.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	0.1
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	15.7
Site - carbon-rich other	0.3
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	2.2
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	52.7
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	25.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	1.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 32c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0184
	{Si}	60.7
	{Al, Si}	7.7
	{Fe}	5.4
	{Ti}	4.8
	{S, Ba-LA1}	3.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.5
	{Si, Fe}	2.2
	{Ca}	1.9
	{Mg, Si}	1.1
	{Al, Si, K}	0.9
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.8
	{Si, S, Ba-LA1}	0.8
	{S, Ba-LA1, Ba-LB1}	0.7
	{Al}	0.7
	{Si, Fe}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Mg, Ca}	0.6
	{S}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Ti}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.0
	{P}	0.0
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.3
Pellet	0.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.6
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	9.1
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.4
Carbon rich - other	0.9
Cement or BOF converter	0.3
Cement	0.7
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	63.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	21.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	1.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	2.1
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	0.1
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	9.1
Site - carbon-rich other	0.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	0.9
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.3
Urban	69.9
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	21.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	1.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels